

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF DYNAMIC WETTING FLOWS INTO FIBROUS MEDIA FOR MACRO/MICRO-VOID CREATION ISSUES DURING LIQUID COMPOSITE MOLDING PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT

A bifluid-solid contact model involving capillary effects is developed to provide an accurate characterization of the fluids and impervious fiber system at the microscopic scale, during Liquid Composite Molding processes. This model is based on the description of two immiscible fluids (Resin/Air) with some special boundary conditions which represent liquid/fiber interactions. The moving fluid interface is described by the level set method, within an Eulerian context. Continuous linear approximations are used for both velocity and pressure stabilized by the Algebraic Sub-Grid Scale method. Different methods for the surface tension term calculation are used to reduce spurious velocities at the fluid interface: surface local reconstruction method for the surface integral; implicit method for the surface curvature calculation. These methods have been validated on both static and dynamic bubble test cases. As for the liquid/fiber interactions, some methods to prescribe the static contact angle have been implemented and validated on spreading drop cases.

1 INTRODUCTION

Capillary and wetting phenomena play a major role for a lot of applications in many fields of engineering, such as lubrication, biology, cosmetic, petroleum... Considering such phenomena requires an accurate description of moving interfaces which ensure the coupling between two immiscible liquids or between a liquid and air. These moving interfaces can deform to minimize their surface energy. The dynamic of interfaces is largely influenced by capillary forces, and the interaction of these fluids with a solid surface gives rise to wetting phenomena. These phenomena are behind the formation of defects (porosities) that can be met in composite material processes, such as Liquid Composite Molding (LCM). LCM processes include Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM), Injection / Compression Moulding (*a.k.a.* CRTM), RTMLight and Resin Infusion (*a.k.a.* Vacuum Assisted RTM). Among them, the Liquid Resin Infusion (LRI) processes (Fig. 2) are sophisticated and competitive techniques for manufacturing high performance composites, especially for large parts in aeronautics. These processes consist in infusing a liquid resin through a stacking of fibrous preforms on which an external mechanical pressure is applied. One of the main bottlenecks arising in such a process is the macro/micro-void formation (Fig. 1), which may significantly affect the quality of the final part. Indeed, this porosity generation is mainly due to the inhomogeneous micro-structure of preforms, which are arrangements of fibre tows (Fig. 2). It leads to a non-uniform permeability and thus induces changes in the flow regime (velocity, pressure). The preform can consequently be partially impregnated depending on the local flow regime. For example, when the flow velocity is high, micro-void formation may occur between filaments inside fiber tows, while macro-voids may be found in the space between fibre tows when the flow velocity is low [1]. Although these phenomena are well known to occur, they are still not well understood and difficult to accurately predict.

Figure 1: Macro/micro-porosities in composite material parts elaborated by resin infusion-based process [2].

The aim of the present work is to provide an accurate characterization of these phenomena at the microscopic scale (Fig. 2) within a finite element framework (using the Z-set finite elements software [5, 15]). At the microscopic scale, the capillarity plays a key role. A local fluid-solid contact model has been developed to model the associated dynamic wetting flows. It involves modelling the surface tension, capillarity and wetting effects between fluids (air and resin) and fibrous solids. The surface tension force is firstly considered for a closed interface between the two immiscible fluids, and then the fluid/fiber interaction, *i.e.* problems regarding to contact lines, is discussed.

Figure 2: Different modelling scale of (LCM) resin infusion-based processes.

2 LOCAL FLUID/SOLID MODEL

We consider here a domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ ($d=2$ or $d=3$) occupied by two immiscible incompressible Newtonian fluids: Ω_A (air) and Ω_R (resin). The bifluid flow is described by one single Stokes system:

$$\begin{cases} -\nabla \cdot (2\eta \underline{\underline{\dot{\epsilon}}}(\vec{v})) + \nabla p = \gamma \kappa \vec{n} \delta(\Gamma) + \rho \vec{g} \\ \nabla \cdot \vec{v} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where \vec{v} is the velocity, p the pressure, $\underline{\underline{\dot{\epsilon}}}(\vec{v}) = (\nabla \vec{v} + \nabla^T \vec{v})/2$ the strain rate tensor, \vec{g} the gravity, $\rho = H\rho_A + (1-H)\rho_R$ the density, $\eta = H\eta_A + (1-H)\eta_R$ the dynamic viscosity. $\eta_{A/R}$, $\rho_{A/R}$ are respectively the viscosities, and densities of the two fluids and H is the Heaviside function:

$$H(\varphi) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \varphi \geq 1 \\ 1, & \text{if } \varphi < 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The moving interface between the two fluids, denoted by Γ , is described by the zero iso-value of the so-called level set function φ [13]. A set of impervious fibers Ω_F , assumed to be non-deformable, is embedded into a surrounding fluid. In this work, fibers are assumed to be rigid bodies, and are consequently represented only through their boundaries $\partial\Omega_F$. The moving interface Γ can either be closed or interact with the fluid/fibers interface $\partial\Omega_F$. In this case, Γ has a boundary $\partial\Gamma$, which corresponds to the so called contact point (blue dots in Fig. 3 with θ the associated contact angle) in 2D case.

Figure 3: Description of the computational domain.

The surface tension force $\vec{F}_\Gamma = \gamma \kappa \vec{n} \delta(\Gamma)$ acts only at the interface Γ . $\delta(\Gamma)$ is the Dirac function defined on the interface only, γ is the surface tension coefficient, κ the curvature of the interface and \vec{n} its normal vector. One advantage of using the level set method to describe the interface Γ is that the normal vector \vec{n} and curvature κ of interface can easily be calculated:

$$\vec{n} = \frac{\vec{\nabla} \varphi}{\|\vec{\nabla} \varphi\|}, \quad \kappa = \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{n} \quad (3)$$

The contact line dynamics is described, for wetting phenomena, by boundary conditions consisting in the enforcement of the contact angle and of slip between fluid and solid. An iterative method is used to prescribe the (static) contact angle [3, 7] (see Sect. 3), while a Navier condition allows us to consider a slip coefficient [3, 11].

3 NUMERICAL METHODOLOGY

In a finite element context, the whole computational domain is discretized by using one single unstructured mesh, made up of triangles (d=2) or tetrahedrons (d=3). Both velocity and pressure fields are approximated by continuous piecewise linear functions. Stability of the discrete Stokes system is

subsequently ensured by using a Variational Multi-Scale (VMS) stabilization method (more precisely, the Algebraic Sub-Grid Scale method [4, 10]). However, one of the key points of the present Eulerian approach is the computation of the surface integral:

$$\int_{\Gamma} \gamma \kappa \vec{n} \cdot \vec{w} dS \quad (4)$$

which is the surface tension term of the weak Stokes' formulation. Two difficulties for computing this term appear: first the computation of an integral onto a surface passing through the mesh element (see Fig. 5); second, the computation of the curvature.

Hence, two ways are investigated for computing this surface integral: the Continuum Surface Force (CSF) method [12], where the surface integral (Eq. (4)) is approximated by a volume integral, and the Surface Local Reconstruction (SLR) method [6], where the surface tension term is explicitly computed over a locally reconstructed interface (Fig. 4). All details concerning both CSF and SLR methods are given in previous works [3, 6]. Moreover, the curvature cannot be computed directly, because the level set function is piecewise linear, and normal vectors are piecewise constant. One solution to overcome this difficulty is to perform a nodal projection of the normal vector field before applying the divergence operator (Eq. (3)). However, the nodal projection can be a source of numerical errors. Thus, a tensorial method has been developed in [6, 14], consisting in considering the weak form of (4). Thus, the explicit calculation of curvature is no longer required, and only the normal vector field is involved in the surface tension term.

Figure 4: CSF method vs. SLR method.

The iterative method allowing the enforcement of the static angle is illustrated in Fig. 5 [3]. We first replace the normal vector \vec{n}_{Γ} , computed from the gradient of the level set function, by \vec{n}_{θ} at the triple junction (Fig. 5). This target vector \vec{n}_{θ} is calculated from the desired angle θ . This modification changes locally the curvature: a force is naturally generated, moving the interface till the desired angle is reached.

Figure 5: Computational procedure to prescribe the static angle.

4 NUMERICAL RESULTS

The developed model is first verified on capillary driven flow test cases: static bubble equilibrium and ellipsoidal bubble evolution under surface tension effect. Finally, numerical simulations of spreading drops on a plane wall have been investigated to highlight wetting phenomena.

The static bubble test case is widely studied in literature to check the convergence and the performance of surface tension computation methods. The test consists in computing the equilibrium of a static bubble placed inside another fluid. The bubble interface is a circle of radius 0.2 m , the fluid domain is a $(1\text{ m} \times 1\text{ m})$ square. The surface tension considered at the interface, γ , is 0.2 N.m^{-1} . The viscosity is 0.1 Pa.s for the fluid inside the bubble and 0.001 Pa.s for the surrounding fluid. The analytical solution of this problem is a zero velocity field and a discontinuous pressure field due to the surface tension effect. The pressure jump across the interface is $\Delta p = \gamma\kappa = 1\text{ Pa}$ according to the Laplace's law. Because of numerical approximations, spurious velocities may be observed at the vicinity of the interface (Fig. 6). Convergence rates for the velocity and pressure are given in a previous work [3], and let show that both SLR and CSF methods have nearly the same precision for pressure fields, while the SLR method seems slightly more precise for the velocity approximation.

Figure 6: Pressure and velocity fields for a static bubble under surface tension effect $\gamma=0.2 \text{ N.m}^{-1}$, viscosity of the fluid into the bubble: 0.1 Pa.s , and for the outer fluid 0.001 Pa.s .

As shown in Fig. 7, the interface (iso-zero value of the level set function φ) of an ellipsoidal bubble turns to a sphere under the surface tension effect. We consider here an ellipse of radius $1 \text{ mm} \times 1 \text{ mm} \times 1.5 \text{ mm}$, enclosed into a cubic domain $5 \text{ mm} \times 5 \text{ mm} \times 5 \text{ mm}$. The surface tension coefficient is 0.03 N.m^{-1} . The viscosity is 0.0003 Pa.s for the ellipsoid bubble and 0.03 Pa.s for the surrounding fluid. Since the volume of the bubble is conserved, the equilibrium shape is the sphere of radius 1.1447 mm , with a pressure jump of 52.4 Pa across the interface. Initial and final states, obtained with the CSF method, are shown in Fig. 7, where only a quarter of the surface is drawn for clarity.

Figure 7: Pressure fields during the evolution of an ellipsoidal bubble under surface tension effect, $\gamma=0.03 \text{ N.m}^{-1}$, viscosity of the bubble: 30 mPa.s , and for the outer fluid 0.3 mPa.s .

We consider now the evolution of a liquid drop, initially a quarter of sphere, in contact with a plane wall. Starting from an initial contact angle of 90° , the flow is computed until the equilibrium shape is achieved. The liquid is subjected to surface tension, and wetting boundary conditions (Sect. 3) are applied to the fluids/solid interface. Here, only a quarter of domain is computed, as shown in Fig. 8. The other part is represented thanks to symmetry conditions: $\vec{v} \cdot \vec{n} = 0$, and θ (contact angle) = 90° , applied to the two lateral sides of the computation domain. The mesh is refined in the drop vicinity to have a correct representation of its geometry. The mesh is made up of 24,458 nodes and 138,688 tetrahedrons with a mesh size from 0.08 mm to 0.5 mm with respect to the distance to the interface.

The changes in drop shapes for a contact angle of 60 ° and 120 ° are presented in Fig. 8. The contact angle evolutions are shown in Fig. 9. These values are the averaged along the drop/wall contact line. The mean value of the contact angle converges toward the prescribed value in 5 ms approximately for a time step of $\Delta t = 0.4$ ms. Further details about numerical errors can be found in [3].

Figure 8: Spreading drop with a contact angle of 60° (top) and 120°(bottom) over a plane substrate under surface tension effect. $\gamma = 0.03$ N.m⁻¹, viscosity of the fluid bubble: 30 mPa.s, and 0.3 mPa.s for the outer fluid.

Figure 9: Contact angles (averaged over the contact line) evolution during spreading drop for different wetting conditions: 60 °, 75 °, 120 ° and 150 °.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this work was to study some problems involving capillarity and wetting, as those typically met in the manufacturing processes by resin infusion. A local fluid-solid contact model has been established to take into account those effects. This model is based on a Eulerian description of two immiscible fluids, governed by Stokes equations, with boundary conditions describing wetting phenomena at fluid/fiber interfaces within a finite element framework. The fluid interface is described

by a level set method, which allows capillary forces to be calculated. Several methods for computing surface tension term have thus been developed and compared on different test cases. Furthermore, numerical methods for enforcing a static contact angle and computing the contact line dynamics have been implemented and validated on spreading drop simulations. Even if more efforts are still necessary for a realistic dynamics of the contact line motion, this work represents a basis for simulating impregnation phenomena in fiber tows which are ongoing.

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